

OPERATIONAL STRATEGY TO IMPROVE ANALYST PERFORMANCE AT JAKARTA IT SERVICE DESK OF ROYAL BLUE ENERGY

Kamilla Sukmahati¹, Yudo Anggoro²

Master of Business Administration Program, Institut Teknologi Bandung, Bandung

E-mail: kamillasukmahati@gmail.com¹, yudo.anggoro@sbm-itb.ac.id²

Received : 01 December 2025

Published : 30 January 2026

Revised : 15 December 2025

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.54443/morfai.v6i2.5072>

Accepted : 10 January 2026

Link Publish : <https://radjapublika.com/index.php/MORFAI/article/view/5072>

Abstract

The Global Service Desk operates 24/7 and covers the entire Royal Blue Company work area in the world, utilizes a ticketing system to handle IT service issues and requests. This study focused on the Jakarta Service Desk (JSD) and analyzed operational performance from January to June 2025. The study aimed to examine the strategies implemented within the JSD and the challenges faced in improving the work performance of each analyst. In a dynamic work environment, increasing ticket volumes, and continuous technological advancements, JSD analysts are expected to survive by achieve the targeted performance. The implemented strategies included weekly training programs conducted by the service excellence team, a self-service portal for users, automation tools (RTBot), shift-left initiatives, weekly role rotation, and more. The analysis used Gap Analysis and the Fishbone Analysis. By identifying gaps in each aspect that impact analyst performance and determining the root cause of the problem, analysts are expected to focus on narrowing the gaps and working on root cause so that results can meet the set targets. The results show that the critical gap in this research is with the Live Interactions per Shift. If this critical gap fixed, this would take effect to others performance like chat & call answer. These findings tell us that the collaboration from each analyst in this desk is required to achieve targets according to KPIs and provide satisfactory service to each user.

Keywords: *Service Desk Performance, Gap Analysis, Fishbone Analysis, Operational Strategy, Analyst Performance*

INTRODUCTION

The Jakarta Service Desk (JSD) handles IT support for the Asia-Pacific region in Royal Blue Energy Company. JSD manages about 900 requests every single day through phones, emails, and chat messages. The desk never closes. Analysts are always available to help internal users 24/7. This research studies the organization's strategy to push performance to the top. Technology kept changing. User expectations are high. Problems got more complicated. So management always up for new strategies to handle the Eastern Hemisphere from Jakarta Service Desk. The strategy run in January-June 2025 like weekly training for all analysts, create automation tools to handle routine requests, get people take certifications, started rotation roles for each analyst every week to take live interactions and email interactions, and appraisal system for quality performance. By mid-2025, enough time had passed to see how all the strategies resulted. The numbers in the JSD Dashboard will show strength the JSD have, and which is the weak that needs to be improved. As the goals are specific, we will measure the actual performance and calculate how far off the target each area is. We will use Critical Path Method to identify which activities slow everything down the most. Next, we will evaluate whether individual strategies accomplish what they're supposed to. Last, we will develop practical recommendations based on evidence rather than assumptions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Global IT Support/Help Desk/Service Desk is a several support technicians and specialists collaborate to solve problems that are reported on help tickets. The IT support serves users across multiple countries and time zones. It requires structured workflows, clear handoffs, and cross-border coordination (Kumar & Liu, 2020). IT Service Management (ITSM) is a collection of frameworks that support organizations managing services (Serrano, Faustino, Adriano, Pereira, & Silva, 2020). A primary ITSM framework is ITIL, which is the most widely adopted standard to align IT services with business objectives (Al-Ashmoery, Haider, Haider, & Nasser, 2021). When

OPERATIONAL STRATEGY TO IMPROVE ANALYST PERFORMANCE AT JAKARTA IT SERVICE DESK OF ROYAL BLUE ENERGY

Kamilla Sukmahati and Yudo Anggoro

companies use ITIL, they often see lower operating expenses, higher efficiency, and better company performance and profitability. But ITIL can be hard to put into practice since it is so complicated.

PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT

Performance Management is the process by the management in the company to align employees' work performance based on target in the company. In Jakarta Service Desk, this performance management usually will be measured using KPI. Performance metrics used in JSD including:

- First Contact Resolution (FCR)
- Service Level Agreement (SLA)
- Averang Handle Time
- Customer Satisfaction Score (CSAT)

These metrics allow management to identify performance gaps, monitor trends, and evaluate the effectiveness of operational strategies implemented. In this research, Performance Management supports the use of Gap Analysis and Fishbone Analysis. These tools help translate performance data into actionable insights, that could make JSD focus to improve the critical areas of the findings.

GAP ANALYSIS

Gap Analysis is a strategic planning tool. It helps businesses figure out what they need to do to get from where they are now to where they want to be in the future. In terms of IT service operation, Gap Analysis is used to compare actual performance and target performance and indicate where improvement is required. The concept was developed from literature on strategic management and has been applied in numerous business contexts. Fundamentally, Gap Analysis addresses the following three questions: Where are we? Where do we want to be? How do we get there?

FISHBONE ANALYSIS

This Fishbone diagram identifies all the potential processes and factors that could contribute to a problem. Fishbone diagram is often called Caused-and-Effect Diagram or Ishikawa Diagram. This introduced by Dr.Kaoru Ishikawa, a quality control expert from Japan, as one of the seven basic quality tools. Fishbone diagram will identify various potential causes of an effect or issues and analyze the problem through a brainstorm session. The issue will be broken down into a number of related categories, including people, materials, machines, procedures, policies, etc. Each categories need to be explained through a brainstorming session. Fishbone analysis begins with determining the problem statement which is the subject matter. The problem that will be solved is the fish head in the diagram. Then determined the category which represents the cause and effect as fish bones. In each categories possible causes of the problem are identified.

Brainstorms are the major categories of causes of the problem. The headings are:

- Method
- Machine
- Material
- Manpower
- Measurement
- Environment

METHOD

This research uses quantitative methods, specifically a descriptive and correlational case study, focused on Jakarta Service Desk of Royal Blue Energy Company. This analysis is based on numbers from the ServiceNow ticketing system, KPI scorecards, and training records. This research period lasts for 6 months, from January to June 2025. This time chosen because it gives enough data (two full quarters) to see the real performance patterns and trends each analyst on this desk.

Frameworks for analyzing data:

1. Gap Analysis: This method was used to compare the actual performance data to the KPI targets in a systematic way. This comparison gave an objective number to the size of the performance gaps in several service areas.
2. Fishbone Analysis: This Fishbone diagram identifies all the potential processes and factors that could contribute to a problem

OPERATIONAL STRATEGY TO IMPROVE ANALYST PERFORMANCE AT JAKARTA IT SERVICE DESK OF ROYAL BLUE ENERGY

Kamilla Sukmahati and Yudo Anggoro

DATA COLLECTION METHOD

This research tracked the total number of tickets entering JSD through each channel:

- Email tickets: Incidents and requests sent to JSD through the ServiceNow portal.
- Phone call tickets: Issues reported through voice calls to the Service Desk hotline.
- Web chat tickets: Users talked to the Service Desk in real time through the ESM portal.

This information was collected every month to show how many people used each channel and how the way people wanted to contact the Service Desk. Every ticket in ServiceNow has a “contact type” category that records how it was submitted. This makes it easy to get this information.

DATA ANALYSIS PROCESS

- a) Organizing the data: The first step is to collect the necessary data from the ESM dashboard.
- b) Data comparison: Compare the data obtained from ESM with the existing targets in the KPI.
- c) Identifying Performance Gaps: Gap analysis is basically figuring out how far away performance is from where it should be. For each statistic, the study identified a target based on industry standards or corporate needs and then figured out how distant JSD was from that target.

The research prioritized gaps by asking three questions:

- a) How big is the gap? Bigger gaps generally got more attention.
- b) How much does it matter? Gaps in metrics that directly affected customers or SLA compliance were more important than nice-to-have improvements.
- c) How easy is it to fix? Some gaps might be easier to close than others with available resources
- d) Fishbone Analysis: To figure out the reasons behind issues that happen in the Jakarta Service Desk.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Gap Analysis

Below is the performance data in JSD from January to June 2025. Each of the KPI category carries a specific weight in the overall performance. Few of them show large gap, while others show the performance meet target achievement.

Table 1. Performance Data Jan-Jun 2025

KPI Category	Metric	Target	Actual Result	Gap
Inbound SLA (10%)	Call answer <60 sec	>85%	77.8%	-7.2
	Chat answer <120 sec	>88%	83.7%	-4.3
Service KPO (35%)	First Contact Resolution	>65%	81.4%	+16.4
	Incident Resolution	>85%	91.78%	+6.78
	Resolved tickets/shift	>12	11.1	-0.9
Interactions (20%)	Live interactions/shift	24	18.24	-5.76
	Email interactions/shift	30	33.15	+3.15
Quality/Training (10%)	Customer Survey Score	>4.5	4.68	+0.18
	Low Score Survey %	<5%	6.85%	-1.85
	Quiz Completion	100%	97.80%	-2.2
	Training Attendance	85%	91.29%	+6.29

GAP CLOSURE REQUIREMENTS

Gap	Current	Target	Required Improvement
Live interactions	18.24	24	+5.76 interactions/shift
Call answer time	77.8%	85%	+7.2% improvement
Chat answer time	83.7%	88%	+4.3% improvement
Resolved tickets	11.1	12	+0.9 tickets/shift
Quiz completion	97.8%	100%	+2.2% improvement
Low survey %	6.85%	<5%	-1.85% reduction

The result shows that Call Answer Time has bigger gap than Live Interactions per Shift. But Live Interactions per Shift carry a 20% weight in overall operational score, when Call Answer Time only 10%. Furthermore, Live Interactions per Shift have a significant effect to other desk performances. By addressing the root cause of this metric, it is essential to improving the overall quality of operations.

FISHBONE ANALYSIS

Based on the performance evaluation data that has been analyzed from January-June 2025, Live Interactions per Shift shows a significant gap compared to other categories. This indicator represents a critical operational issue because live interactions are directly related to real-time service availability, response time, and customer experience. To conduct the root cause of this gap, fishbone analysis was conducted using four main dimensions: Manpower, Method, Techonology, and Environment.

Figure I. Fishbone Diagram for Live Interactions per Shift

1) Manpower

The data shows that live interactions and email interactions’s result are not balance. Email interactions per shift exceed target and this indicated a limited real-time ticket handling capacity among analysts. With First Contact Resolution and Incident Resolution exceed their targets, this suggest that the analysts are technically capable of resolving issues, but less efficient in handling the real-time interactions (chat & call). This impact to the number of live interactions handled per shift, and leading to higher queue time, and increased waiting time for users which potential risks to call and chat SLA performance.

2) Method

Several strategies have been implemented to manage workload distribution, including weekly role rotation. But based on the performance results, these strategies have not effectively increased live interactions. There is no operational rule to prioritize the live interactions over email handling during high-volume periods. This impact to the performance result.

3) Technology

Current operational technologies do not have tools strategy specifically designed to support fast live interaction handling. The ticketing system tools support resolution quality they do not significantly reduce handling time during live interaction. The data in this thesis indicates good resolution but low interaction volume suggest that Average Handle Time (AHT) for live interactions remains high. This condition often caused by the absence of quick access knowledge tools, automation, or system features that assist analysys during real-time conversations. With the technology support to accelerate live handling, analysts can only handle limited number of live interactions per shift, directly contributing to the performance gap.

4) Environment

Service Desk operates in high-demand environment, where analysts face overlapping chats and calls interactions. Handling multiple live interactions increase workload and reduces focus. This condition could increase delayed responses and longer handling times. This will impact to the analyst's ability to complete the target of the day.

CONCLUSION

Overall, JSD's current strategies are effective. The data shows strong performance in First Contact Resolution, incident resolution within target, training attendance, and customer satisfaction, which indicates that strategies such as training, shift-left, and knowledge support are helping analysts resolve issues effectively and maintain service quality. However, these strategies are not yet effective in improving real-time responsiveness and live handling capacity. The biggest performance gap is Live Interactions per Shift, and this gap is linked to call/chat SLA shortfalls. This indicates that operational design (role assignment, prioritization rules, and live handling enablement) still needs improvement.

REFERENCES

- Axelos. (2019). ITIL Foundation, ITIL 4 Edition. TSO (The Stationery Office).
- Kelley, J. E., & Walker, M. R. (1959). Critical-path planning and scheduling. *Proceedings of the Eastern Joint Computer Conference*, 16, 160–173.
- Kumar, A., & Liu, S. (2020). Analyzing performance of a global help desk team operation–country handoffs, efficiencies and costs. *IEEE Computer Society*.
- Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Berry, L. L. (1988). SERVQUAL: A multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality. *Journal of Retailing*, 64(1), 12–40.
- Kaplan, R. S., & Norton, D. P. (1996). *The Balanced Scorecard: Translating Strategy into Action*. Harvard Business Press.
- Kaufman, R. A., & Mann, A. (1993). *Needs assessment: A user's guide*. Educational Technology.
- Sharma, Y., & Bhatia, D. (2023). *SLA Management in Intent-Driven Service Management Systems: A Taxonomy and Future Directions*. *ACM Computing Surveys*.
- Teece, D. J., Pisano, G., & Shuen, A. (1997). Dynamic capabilities and strategic management. *Strategic Management Journal*, 18(7), 509–533.